

THE PROBLEM OF NEOLOGISMS ON THE INTERNET**Ganiyeva Makhliyo**

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Abstract: The development of network communications has led to a sharp increase in the number of new words and expressions. The creation of a new vocabulary reflected radical cultural transformations that entailed a change in the picture of the world. The Internet has become a space for the invention and recording of neologisms in speech, a universal platform for collective word creation - the variety of genres of network communication has entailed an expansion of the capabilities of ordinary participants in Internet discourse in terms of creating neologisms. Studying the new vocabulary in the Internet space allows us to highlight the patterns of the functioning of neologisms at the current stage of language development.

Key words: neologisms, network communication, Internet, social media, linguistics, discourse.

Introduction. The progress of electronic technologies has become one of the main reasons for the development of language, which is reflected primarily in lexical transformations [1]. The formation of neologisms in the online environment is a fruitful lexical transformation, most clearly reflecting the specifics of language adaptation to cultural and social innovations. The appearance of new words and expressions, as well as shifts in the semantic plan of familiar lexemes, is associated with the specifics of the functioning of the Internet, and the network space is both a place for the constant generation of new vocabulary and its fixation in texts and speech, which leads to the further spread of neologisms both on the Internet, and beyond, in everyday speech. "The Internet has firmly entered the life of modern man, including having a huge impact on his language, which, like any developing system, is also rapidly adapting to new conditions. First of all, changes are noticeable in vocabulary. Modern man is

surrounded by a large number of borrowings, abbreviations and neologisms, changing the meaning of old familiar words, increasing new meanings. The Internet is both one of the reasons for such changes, and a kind of “archiver” through which we can trace all these processes” [2,135]. The Internet acts as an engine for the generation of new words and expressions, since it is a complex mechanism for transforming linguistic realities, intuitively understandable to users. “The process of forming verbal Internet formations in a language is simple, but at the same time high-tech, since communication technologies themselves are the reasons for the emergence of new words” [2,135]. The very emergence of networkisms is associated with the expansion of electronic communication capabilities - new network resources naturally give rise to a certain number of new lexemes. The Internet is becoming a space for using the entire palette of linguistic means to create new words and rethink familiar vocabulary, which also joins neologisms after changing its original semantic plan. The process of neologization in the online environment is associated with the continuity of changes in the context of the functioning of words and the variability of the use of tropes by the creators of new vocabulary. “With the advent of new Internet resources, neologisms also appear. When they are formed, the entire arsenal of language capabilities is used”. Network neologisms are the result of the continuous development of network communication and are spreading among a wide range of Internet users, in particular, in the space of numerous social networks. “An Internet neologism is a new, borrowed word that arises during the period of active development of worldwide Internet communication, becomes widespread in a certain area and is perceived during this period by the majority of native speakers among users of social networks” [3,14]. Network neologisms or networkisms are perceived by the collective consciousness Internet discourse due to the fact that they are the fruit of the creativity of ordinary participants in network communication. The researcher believes that “The Internet language of the early 21st century characterized by the active production of lexical innovations. Neologisms are traditionally viewed as the result of dynamic processes that reflect the adaptation of language to transformations occurring in the political,

economic and social spheres of human activity. These changes are characteristic, first of all, of the lexical and grammatical systems of the language" [4,4]. The dynamic process of displacement and formation of new words in the network space is one of the most interesting topics in modern linguistic research [4,5]. The researcher connects the use of neologisms in online communication with the desire to create an expressive style that has bright shades of speech and conveys the emotional mood of the author. We believe that the invention of expressive neologisms is largely due to the fact that the authors of Internet texts try to compensate for the inevitable loss of the emotional component in online communication by expanding the emotional sound and expressive power of a new word - previously, parapheme means were mainly considered as means of compensating for the loss of the emotional component such as emoticons and emojis, which are a surrogate for a direct emotional reaction [5,16].

Conclusion. The process of word formation in the network space is associated with the phenomenon of derivation: "In the sphere of the Internet space, word formation processes are in full swing. Neologisms are actively formed on the basis of both morphological and semantic derivation. Especially, productive methods of word formation are: acronymization; abbreviation; reverse construction; metaphorical transfer. Word-formation games, the addressee of a journalistic text becomes involved in the most interesting process of solving an intellectual puzzle, bringing him aesthetic pleasure.

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